

PLANT MEDIATED SYNTHESIS OF MAGNETITE NANO PARTICLES AND ITS APPLICATIONS IN DIVERSE FIELDS-A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT: Nanotechnology and nanomaterials are two of the rapidly growing fields in science now a day. Hydrothermal, sol-gel, laser-ablation, electrochemical, and thermal processes are among the most traditional ways to synthesise nanoparticles. Iron nanoparticles synthesised by biogenic means provide a number of merits over traditional methods, such as the fact that they are non-polluting, simple, inexpensive, and do not pose any health risks to humans. Nanoparticles of magnetite have been extensively used in medicinal and industrial applications because of their distinct features. In many applications, precise control of nanoparticle morphology and size is essential. Plant extract content, temperature, and pH all influence the size of the nanoparticles that develop. It provides an overview of the plant-mediated production of magnetite nanoparticles, probable chemicals, and mechanisms that may be involved in the reduction process, and their potential applications in a variety of fields.

Key words: Magnetite nanoparticles, Bio-medical applications, Plant mediated synthesis

1. INTRODUCTION

The latest progress in nanotechnology had a significant impact on a wide range of industries. Humans have placed their faith in nanotechnology and feel that Nano research can improve their existing living standard, thanks to the recent development and expansion of technology. [1] Inorganic and organic nanoparticles are submicron moieties with diameters between 1 and 100 nm that have distinct properties when compared to bulk materials [2]. Most nanotechnology researchers employ metal and metal oxide nanoparticles in their work now a day. Magnetite (Fe_3O_4) is the most widely used iron oxide due to its excellent biocompatibility with low toxicity [3, 4]. Smaller iron oxide MNPs are the ideal choice for biomedical and biological applications. [5]

The change in physicochemical properties can alter the surface chemistry of MNPs and that's why they are used in Hypothermia, MRI, Immuno assays, drugs and cell separation [6,7]. These nanoparticles (MNPs) have broad applications in the biological and environmental fields because of their large surface area and metal-rich moiety. For this reason, magnetite nanoparticles are a popular research subject among scientists all over the world [8-10]. This is because their unique properties such as shape, size, and distribution make them ideal for different applications.

2. MAGNETITE NANOPARTICLES

Iron oxides such as magnetite, magnetic iron ore, and loadstone, are ancient magnetic materials [11]. Because of its spinel structure and the Fe_3O_4 chemical formula, this type of iron oxide possesses the strongest magnetic of all the iron oxide phases. The three naturally occurring forms of these oxides are hematite (Fe_2O_3), magnetite (Fe_3O_4), and magnetite (Fe_3O_4). Several interesting qualities may be found in each of these forms, such as reduced toxicities, low oxidation sensitivities, improved magnetic response stability, ease of synthesis and treatment

of the surface, and the ability to transition to superparamagnetic form by reducing particle sizes. The behavior of these magnetite nanoparticles is more appropriate [12-18].

Indeed, magnetite has been used in a wide range of industries, and it is the most widely used iron oxide. Magnetic iron oxide (Fe_3O_4) is a mineral and one of the conventional natural iron oxides. An inverse spinel pattern with alternate tetrahedral-octahedral layers is visible in the magnetite crystal structure. As a result of the higher CFSE, in Fe_3O_4 , Fe^{2+} species occupy half of the octahedral lattice positions. There are two octahedral and two tetrahedral lattice sites for Fe^{3+} species, which fill the rest of the space [19].

3. MAGNETIC PROPERTIES

These iron oxides have a variety of magnetic characteristics, including superparamagnetic, paramagnetic, ferro, ferri, and antiferromagnetic. In the absence of external magnetic field there is no net magnetization because of the randomly aligned magnetic moments. But in the presence of magnetic field they show net magnetization due to the presence of moments oriented in direction of the field completely or partially. It is possible to eliminate the external field without disturbing the parallel order of the magnetic moments in ferromagnetic crystals. Materials that have the same antiparallel moments but no net magnetization are called "antiferromagnetic." [20-21] Ferromagnetic materials' net magnetization is not zero even when moment alignments are antiparallel [22–25], due to differences in the vector lengths of these moments. The orientation may be different for different magnetic structures [25].

4. NANOPARTICLE SYNTHESIS

In the field of nano technology the most important step is the synthesis. The commonly used techniques are top-down and bottom-up methods [26].

In the breakdown (top-down) technique, a solid is broken up into smaller pieces by applying external force to it. Another way is the bottom-up method, which uses atomic or molecular condensations to create nanoparticles from gas or liquid atoms. Top-down methods include both dry and wet grinding. The wet method is better at reducing the condensation of nanoparticles than the dry method. As opposed to the top-down strategy, which includes both gaseous phase approaches and liquid phase procedures, the bottom-up approach includes both. There are a number of factors to consider while selecting a method.

The methods for the synthesis of magnetic nanoparticles include the sol-gel method [27], son chemical method [28], hydrothermal method [29], microwave heating, spray pyrolysis [30], co-precipitation [31], biological route [32], polyol methods [33,34], thermal decomposition [35], solvothermal method [36], micro-emulsions [37], combustion and oxygenation methods [38].

Many authors have used co-precipitation method for the synthesis of iron oxides in stoichiometric proportions from Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} . This method is easy to use, well-known, and adaptable to a variety of situations [39].

4. BIOLOGICAL METHOD OF NANOPARTICLE SYNTHESIS

Biological synthesis of metallic nanoparticle has attracted marked attention in recent years. Microorganisms and plants are used in the biogenic synthesis method to produce nanoparticles [40]. In comparison to certain other physicochemical methods of manufacturing, biosynthesis may produce nanoparticles with a more specified size and morphology [41]. The microbial-based synthesis technique has been proven to be adaptable, environment friendly and compatible with the utilization of product for pharmaceutical purposes, but it is often more expensive than the production of plant-based materials. Plant-based synthesis has more advantages than traditional chemical and physical synthesis. For the large-scale synthesis of nanoparticles, green synthesis is a more environmentally benign, less expensive, and readily scale-up technique. This method cannot involve toxic chemicals and there is no requirement of high temperature and pressure [42]. A green chemical technique, biosynthesis of nanoparticles utilises the biomolecules produced by biomass to both reduce and stabilise the nanoparticle. Due to its simplicity and speed, plant-based nanoparticle production has become an in vogue topic in recent years [43]. The plant extract is simply combined with the metal salt solution in the nanoparticle synthesis method [44].

5. FACTORS EFFECTING BIOSYNTHESIS OF NANOPARTICLES

Synthesis, characterization and applications of NP's depend up on the following factors.

5.1. P^{H}

In the plant-mediated synthesis of nanoparticles, the P^{H} of the solution is important. Several studies have found that the P^{H} of a solution affects the size, shape, and rate of nanoparticle synthesis [45]. This occurs as a result of the formation of nucleation centres, which increases as pH increases. The reduction of metallic ions to metal NPs increases as the nucleation centre increases. The rate of reduction of metal salt and activity of the functional groups in the plant extract depends on P^{H} of the solution [46].

5.2. Temperature

Another key component that determines the size, shape, and rate of nanoparticles is temperature. Temperature increases the formation of nucleation centres, which increases the rate of biosynthesis.

5.3. Time

The size and shape of nanoparticles prepared by plant-based materials depends on time of the reaction mixture and medium.

5.4. Plant extract dosage

The nanoparticle synthesis efficiently depends on plant extract concentration. It is noted that increase in bio mass concentration increases the number of nanoparticles produced. And also it changes the shape of prepared nanoparticles. So there is a need to optimize concentration of bio mass for the process [47,48].

6. PROBABLE MECHANISM FOR SYNTHESIS OF METAL NP'S USING PLANT EXTRACT

Plants and microbes uses the same mechanism for the synthesis of nanoparticles. Metal salts are first reduced by atoms using reducing agents then they come together to form small crystal and then they grow into particles [49]. what is actual process behind the nanoparticle production is not yet to be known by many of the researchers [50].

To manage the shape, size, dispersion, and crystallinity of metal NPs, a novel approach is required in this field. Metallic nanoparticles can be made in a variety of ways. [51]. Polyphenolic acids and polyphenolic sugars are two secondary metabolites that play a major role in the formation of metal NPs. Terpenoids are a potent antioxidant class of organic polymers with a five-carbon isoprene chain. An FTIR analysis discovered

that Cinnamon zeylanisum extract contains terpenoids that can bind metal ions. Notably, polyphenolic chemicals like flavonoids and chalcones are just a few of the many flavonoids kinds. These chemicals enabled metal ion reduction and chelation [52]. Because quercetin is both a flavanoid and potent chelating agent, it can chelate at 3 points. These compounds are used to chelate a no.of metal ions such as Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺, Cu²⁺, Al³⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions[53].

The size and distribution of metal nanoparticles can be determined by the amount of polyphenols in the plant extract. Zinc and other metal ions can be decreased by Azadirecta indica leaf extract's reducing sugars. This produces metallic and bimetallic nanoparticle. [54] The surface active substances flavonoids and terpenoids in azadirecta indica leaf extract make metal nanoparticles stable [55]. A reducing agent, a stabilising agent, and a solvent medium can all be utilised to stabilise the target metal [56]. The presence of pi –electrons and carbonyl groups in their molecular structures play a role in the adsorption of reducing agents [57]. The carbonyl group present in *C.album leaf extract* have an influence on the reduction process[58].

Previous research suggests that nanoparticles are formed by heterogeneous nucleation followed by crystal growth and Ostwald ripening. Extraneous catalytic compounds produced by plant biomass can act as a framework for crystal formation. Crystallization and Ostwald ripening increase crystal size range. Ostwald ripening occurs during production for a variety of metal nanoparticles, when smaller particles move to larger particles nearby to enlarge the latter and deplete the former [59, 60].

Sugars in plant extracts can also generate metal nanoparticles. Glucose, a monosaccharide, is a reducing agent. Also, by converting ketone to aldehydes in the tautomer, fructose may act as an antioxidant. Because tautomeric shift limits fructose's antioxidant action, glucose is a powerful reducing agent [61]. Plant extracts are commonly heated to 90°C to denature enzymes during synthesising. It is hypothesised that phytochemicals such as flavonoids and sesquiterpenes, coupled with their functional groups, are involved in capping and reducing nanoparticles. Polysaccharide hydroxyl and carboxyl groups were crucial in the transformation of metal salts into metal NPs. Amino groups in polysaccharides can stabilise nanoparticles [62, 63]. To stabilise nanoparticles in dispersive fluids, an opposing force to the Vander wall force must be present [64]. Static or electrostatic stability can act as repulsive forces. Smaller particles accumulating generate nanoparticles of various shapes. Other parameters, such as plant biomass and reaction conditions, may also influence nanoparticle production. [65]

TABLE -1: SYNTHESIS OF MAGNETITE NP'S BY VARIOUS PLANT EXTRACTS.

S.No	Plant Extract	Shape	Particle size nm	Ref.
Leaves Extract				
1	<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	crystalline	1-5	[66]
2	<i>Aloe vera</i>	crystalline	6–30	[67]
3	<i>Carica papaya</i>	plate like	33	[68]
4	<i>Cynometra ramiflora</i>	Crystalline	----	[69]
5	<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i>	spherical	10-15	[70]

6	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	irregular sphere	20	[71]
7	<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	Irregularspherical	80	[72]
8	<i>Artemisia annua</i>	Spherical	3–10	[73]
9	<i>Green tea</i>	Spherical	5.7	[74]
10	<i>Sesbania grandiflora</i>	Agglomerated non-spherical	25-60	[75]
11	<i>Lagenaria siceraria</i>	Cubic	30–100	[76]
12	<i>Rubus glaucus</i>	Aggregated Spherical	40–70	[77]
13	<i>Oolong tea</i>	Spherical	45	[78]
14	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	Spherical	65	[79]
15	<i>Kappaphycus lvarezii</i>	Spherical	14.7	[80]
16	<i>Amaranthus dubius</i>	Spherical		[81]
17	<i>Gardenia jasminoides</i>	rock-like	32	[82]
18	<i>Melaleuca nesophila</i>	Spherical	40–60	[83]
19	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Chain-like	40- 80n	[84]
20	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	spherical	3–8	[85]
21	<i>Averrhoa carambola</i>	spherical	32	[86]
22	<i>Cynara cardunculus</i>	semispherical	13	[87]
23	<i>Excoecariacochinchinensis</i>	spherical	25	[88]
24	<i>Plantago major</i>	spherical	4–30	[89]
25	<i>Calliandra haematocephala</i>	bead-like spherical	7	[90]

26	<i>Myrtus communis L leaf aqueous extract</i>	cubic	10-12	[91]
27	<i>Ficus hispida L.</i>	cubic inverse spinel	10-12	[92]
28	<i>Wrightia tinctoria aqueous</i>	rhombic shape	105-145	[93]
29	<i>Wedelia urticifolia (Blume) DC.</i>	rod shape	15-20	[94]
30	<i>Zanthoxylum armatum DC.</i>	spherical	17	[95]
<i>Other Parts of Plant extracts</i>				
31	<i>Citrus reticulata Root</i>	Peel spherical	50	[96]
32	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i>	spherical	25–35	[97]
33	<i>Juglans regia Husk</i>	Cubic shape	9.7–15.4	[98]
34	<i>Mimosa pudica Root</i>	spherical and crystalline	67 nm	[99]
35	<i>Punica granatum Peel</i>	Amorphous	----	[100]
36	<i>Syzygium cumini Seed</i>	spherical fcc	20	[101]
37	<i>Vitis vinifera Stem</i>	core shell structure	<50	[102]
38	<i>Passiflora tripartita</i>	Spherical	18.2–24.7	[103]
39	<i>Averrhoa carambola</i>	Spherical	1.9–3.1	[104]
40	<i>Potato</i>	cubic	40	[105]
41	<i>Arabic gum</i>	spherical	70-80	[106]
42	<i>Tangerine peel</i>	Spherical	50	[107]
43	<i>Plantain peel</i>	Spherical	50	[108]

44	<i>Quince (Cydonia oblonga Miller) seed</i>	spherical	25	[109]
45	<i>Peltophorum Pterocarpum pod</i>	spherical	68–78	[110]

7. CHARACTERIZATION OF MGNP

The changes in size and morphology of magnetite NPs can alter their physical and chemical properties. BET and DLS procedures are used to calculate the surface area and particle size. Transmission electron microscopy and scanning electron microscopy can be used to determine the surface morphology of MNPs. As a result of the photographs we get from this technology, we can figure out how big they are. The Atomic force microscopy technique can be used to detect surface roughness, step height, and the location of scattered particles, in these techniques the TEM can be used to obtain information about the NPs' composition, shape, and size. Material composition and surface topography are revealed by SEM. XRD technique can be used to determine the size of a sample. There are numerous applications for TEM, including determination of crystallinity, the condition of NP aggregation, lattice spacing, and the electron phase shift [111,112]. Calculation of NP size based on XRD sharp peak peaks is accomplished by solving for a and b in the Scherrer formula. Particle size and distribution can be calculated using photon correlation and Mossbauer spectroscopy, as well as DLS methods. Devices such as X-ray fluorescence spectrometer and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy can be used to determine the elemental composition and surface morphology of samples. Composition and chemical state of elements in NPs can be determined using the XPS method. Element composition and elemental analysis of prepared MNPs can be determined using the Energy Dispersive X-ray diffraction approach [113].

8. APPLICATIONS OF MAGNETITE NANOPARTICLES

The properties of the formed NPs are depending on physical parameters including crystal phase, size, shape, capping efficiency (surface area), and charge [114]. Super-exchange in iron oxides magnetically combines unpaired electrons from Fe³⁺ orbitals with electrons from O²⁻ p orbitals. Iron oxides are widely used as pigments in paints and porcelain. Magnetic capsules are widely used in health and business. Among other processes, hematite and magnetite have been utilised as catalysts in the manufacture of NH₃, natural gas desulfurization, and large-scale butadiene synthesis [115-117].

Magnetic nanoparticle uses in biomedicine can be classified as intra- or extra (in vivo, in vitro). In vitro, it is utilised for separation, selection, and magneto relaxometry, whereas in vivo, it is used for therapeutic and diagnostic purposes [118-120]. In vivo, particle size and surface function are critical characteristics. Even if surface ligands aren't targeted, SPIO diameters effect in vivo bio distribution [121].

8.1 NMR IMAGING

With the advent of NMR imaging for clinical diagnosis, a new type of medications called magneto-pharmaceuticals was required. These drugs are given to patients to know the difference between normal and sick tissue, or to reflect organ function or blood flow. MRI is a very effective diagnostic tool in clinical practise. External magnetic fields excite water's hydrogen nuclei, causing them to align antiparallel to the magnetic field. Due to the high magnetic susceptibility of magnetic centres, tissue with high concentrations of nanoparticles has a darker MR image than the surrounding biological background [122].

8.2. THERAPEUTIC APPLICATIONS- HYPERTHERMIA:

In 1957, magnetic particles were utilised to treat hyperthermia. (Gilchrist) Radiation or chemotherapy can be made more effective by increasing medication perfusion and oxygenation by 39°C to 42°C. Temperature increases of 41°C-46°C can cause protein breakdown, disrupting vital cell functions and causing apoptosis (programmed cell death). Carbonization, coagulation, and necrosis occur at temperatures above 45°C [123]. By employing magnetic fluid alone, hyperthermia has been studied in vitro and in vivo [124]. These MNPs were coated with stabilisers or enclosed in delivery Nano carriers, such as liposomes [125].

8.3 DRUG DELIVERY

Drug targeting is a cutting-edge approach of medicine delivery. [126] Iron oxide magnetic nanoparticles have becoming increasingly popular in medication targeting. To deliver MNPs to a specified target site, an external magnetic field or magnetic implants can be used (magnetic drug targeting) [127]. It is possible to coat these particles with inorganic metals and oxides or organic polymers to make them more biocompatible and attachable to bioactive molecules [128,129].

Current drug delivery technologies can't target specific regions of action and have limited drug diffusion through biological barriers, but IONPs coated with polymers, lipids, or inorganics may be able to do this type of reactions [130]. Drugs can be loaded onto magnetic cores in two ways: adsorption onto functionalized NPs or inclusion into an organic/inorganic matrix built over the core. Using magnetic nanoparticles as delivery vectors is favourable [131]. SPIOs coated with Stimuli responsive polymer have lately acquired popularity in targeted delivery and cancer therapy [132].

8.4 CANCER TREATMENT

Mainstays of cancer treatment are chemotherapy and therapeutic nucleic acids. Chemotherapeutics are small-molecule drugs with cytotoxic, cytostatic, or antineoplastic properties [133]. Chemotherapeutics like paclitaxel [134] and cisplatin [135] have been coupled with IONP drug delivery vehicles. Using target-specific IONP formulations for cancer therapy can reduce unwanted side effects while increasing dose to damaged tissue. There are two ways to collect NPs near a tumor: passive or active targeting [136].

8.5 BIOSENSORS AND IMMUNOASSAYS

Magnetite nanoparticles are extensively used in biosensor and immunoassay designs for the immobilisation, separation, and amount of the analyse target prior to detection by transducer elements and magnetic platforms. Magnetic resonance-based detection and magneto resistive sensors are two types of magnetic transducer concepts [137].

8.6 MAGNETORELAXOMETRY

It was first explored for immunoassay evaluation [138]. Magneto relaxometry measures the relaxation of the total magnetic moment of a system of Magnetite NPs in the absence of a magnetic field [139]. There are two relaxation techniques. Initial Néel relaxation [140], occurs when the internal magnetization vector of a nanoparticle relaxes along the easy axis inside the core. Brownian relaxation [141] allows particles to rotate in a carrier liquid. Neel and Brownian relaxation durations can be distinguished [142].

8.7. BIOSEPARATION

To investigate certain biological things (DNA, proteins, and cells), they must be removed from their original context. Superparamagnetic iron oxide particles, for example, are commonly used in bioprocesses for cell separation and purification [143-145]. Because of their high surface area and small size MNPs outperform micrometer-sized resins or beads in bio separation applications. The method involves immobilising oligonucleotides on MNPs, binding them to target nucleic acids in crude cell lysates, and then magnetically separating DNA and RNA [146].

8.8 CATALYSIS APPLICATIONS.

Now a days MNP-supported catalysts have been widely used to improve heterogeneous catalysis constraints. Catalysts that are small and magnetically separable could combine the benefits of high dispersion and reactivity with ease of separation [147]. Carbon-carbon cross-coupling reactions, hydro formylation [148], hydrogenation, and polymerization reactions are only a few of the transition metal-catalysed reactions that have recently emerged using catalytic sites grafted onto Magnetite NPs [149].

8.9. ENVIRONMENTAL APPLICATIONS

The world's most difficult concerns in the coming decades will be related to air quality. Magnetic nanoparticles are presently being explored by scientists and engineers in all of these domains. Magnetic nanoparticles may have the greatest impact on aquatic ecosystem treatment by eliminating industrial contaminants and improving groundwater and marine water quality. In situ applications of nanoscale iron particles are also very versatile. Catalysed and modified iron NPs have been developed to fasten the environmental remediation process [150]. Other MNPs have recently been investigated for removing organic and inorganic pollutants. There are less numbers of articles regarding removing large amounts of organic chemicals, especially dyes. MNPs can remove significant quantities of organic substances [151-153]. Dye is found in many industrial effluent streams, including dyeing, textile, tannery, and paint. The development of functionalized sorbents for selective metal ion removal from complicated matrices is critical. MNPs act as sorbents for metal ions. Because MNPs have a larger surface area than micron-sized sorbents, they are more efficient at removing metal ions [154-156].

TABLE -2: APPLICATIONS OF MAGNETITE NANOMATERIALS

S.No	Plant Name	Application	Ref
1	<i>Sageretia thea</i>	Anti-bacterial activity	[157]
2	<i>Punica granatum</i>	antibacterial activity	[158]
3	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	antibacterial	[159]
4	<i>Stachys lavandulifolia</i>	antibacterial	[160]
5	<i>Annona squamosa</i>	Anti-cancer activity	[161]
6	<i>Sargassum muticum, seaweed</i>	Anti-cancer activity	[162]
7	<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Anti-cancer activity	[163]
8	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Anti-bacterial, Anti-fungal and MRI	[164]
9	<i>Daphne mezereum.</i>	Dye-decolonization	[165]
10	<i>Ficus carica</i>	degradation of dyes	[166]

11	<i>Dolichos lablab L</i>	Crystal Violet	[167]
12	<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Bromothymol blue degradation	[168]
13	<i>Green tea</i>	Degradation of aqueous cationic and anionic dyes	[169]
14	<i>Eucalyptus Tereticornis L , Eucalyptus tereticornis</i>	Adsorption of azo dyes	[170]
15	<i>Melaleuca nesophila, and Rosemarinus officinalis</i>	Decolourisation of azo dyes	[171]
16	<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	Antibacterial	[172]
17	<i>Punica granatum</i>	Hexavalent chromium removal	[173]
18	<i>Green tea and eucalyptus</i>	Nitrates removal	[174]
19	<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i>	Antibacterial	[175]
20	<i>Oolong tea extract</i>	Degrade malachite green (MG).	[176]
21	<i>grape leaf extract</i>	degradation of dye, acid Orange II	[177]
22	<i>Mentha spicata L.</i>	Removal of arsenic	[178]
23	<i>Amaranthus dubius</i>	Anti-oxidant , degradation of dye	[179]
24	<i>Agrewia optica and Prunus persica</i>	Anti-oxidant and anti-bacterial activity	[180]
25	<i>Cynometra Ramiflora</i>	Anti- bacterial activity and dye degradation	[181]
26	<i>Mangolia Champaca ,Mangifera Indica, , Azadirachta Indica and Murraya Koenigii</i>	Nitrate, Phosphateremoval, COD	[182]
27	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	Total nitrogen removal and COD	[183]
28	<i>Tridax Procumbens</i>	Anti-bacterial activity	[184]
29	<i>Zanthoxylum armatum DC</i>	Methylene blue dye degradation	[185]
30	<i>Pomegranate leaves</i>	Congo Red dye degradation	[186]

9. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVE

This review study covers the current research advancements in the field of plant extract-based iron nanoparticle synthesis and explores the numerous mechanisms that have been proposed to explain it. The production of magnetite nanoparticles is facilitated by the usage of plants and their extracts. We should be able to fine-tune the properties of NPs by working with plants. Plant-derived nanoparticles have found utility in a variety of fields. Plant extracts have been used to synthesize magnetite nanoparticles, however the actual method of synthesis is still a mystery. Nanoparticles made from green synthesis can be used to protect the environment. The reaction conditions can be changed to adjust the form and size of the nanoparticles. We are only at the beginning stages of the production of nanoparticles utilising plant extracts. The bio reduction of metallic nanoparticles is thought to be aided by flavonoids, terpenoids, proteins, and alkaloids [187].

These magnetic nanoparticles have a huge variety of applications including bioremediation and electronics as well as antimicrobial textiles and catalytic and medicinal use. Biosynthesis of magnetite nanoparticles using plant extract and their biological uses are the focus of this review. Plant extracts play stabilizing and lowering roles in the production of nanoparticles. The majority of these studies have been conducted in labs at a modest scale, but large-scale exploration and application of nanoparticles in various domains is required. Analytical and positive research is required to design and construct MNPs for a broad range of applications in diverse sectors.

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